

Artificial Intelligence – Some Ethical Issues in the Context of State Government

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Abstract

Introduction: The application of artificial intelligence (AI) has been steadily increasing in diverse spheres of life, such as technologies, economics, education, art and culture, even in politics and others. What is more, the everyday life has been deeply impacted by the development of the AI. As AI is possibly to become integrated into the operations of state governments worldwide, ethical concerns emerge, regarding the extent of AI's autonomy in decision-making and action execution. This research article, therefore, delves into the ethical dimensions of AI deployment within the context of state government and public relations, focusing on two distinct usage scenarios. In the first scenario, AI serves as a tool for information analysis and recommendation without executing decisions or actions autonomously. The second scenario involves AI systems with the authority to independently execute decisions and actions that require the imperative human oversight. Human involvement is essential to ensure that decisions made by AI align with societal values, uphold legal and ethical standards, and safeguard against unforeseen consequences. This dual-tier approach, combining AI's capabilities with human confirmation, strikes a balance between technological advancement and ethical responsibility.

Aim: This study aims to provide certain guidelines for policymakers and technologists in navigating the ethical complexities of AI implementation in the public sector.

Method: The study employs a comparative analysis approach to assess the ethical considerations surrounding AI's autonomy in state government and public relations. It examines the differing needs of AI systems in two distinct scenarios, offering insights into the balance between AI autonomy and human oversight.

Findings: The research findings emphasize the importance of a dual-tier approach in state government AI deployment.

Originality and value: This research contributes to the emerging field of AI ethics by specifically addressing the ethical challenges posed by AI in state government and public relations. The value of the research is set to outline the framework of future solutions and it puts forth the question of the influence of the AI regarding state governments and policymakers, thus focusing on the ethical implications of AI integration.

Key Words: Artificial Intelligence, SWOT Analysis, Ethical Issues, State Government, AI Autonomy, Decision-Making, Human Oversight, Ethical Guidelines.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a milestone in human history. Development is a value people has always been striving for. AI is a phenomenon that is making history and is going to shape the new image of modern-day societies and coming civilization. The application of artificial intelligence (AI) has been steadily increasing in diverse spheres of life, from E-health and online public services to economics, education, art and culture, even in politics and others. What is more, the everyday life has been deeply impacted by the development of AI technologies. As AI is possibly to become integrated into the operations of state governments worldwide, ethical concerns emerge, regarding the extent of AI's autonomy in decision-making and action execution.

This research delves into the ethical dimensions of AI deployment within the context of state government and public relations, focusing on two distinct usage scenarios that are going to be further presented. The study **aims** to turn policymakers and technologists' attention to the ethical complexities of AI implementation in the public sector. The study **employs** a comparative analysis approach to assess the ethical considerations surrounding AI's autonomy in state government and public relations. It examines the differing needs of AI systems in two distinct scenarios, offering insights into the balance between AI autonomy and human oversight. In order to comprehensively examine the intricacies and implications of artificial intelligence, this article also employs a SWOT analysis framework. The research **findings** emphasize the importance of a dual-tier approach in state government AI deployment. This research **contributes** to the emerging field of AI ethics by specifically addressing the ethical challenges posed by AI in state government and public relations. The value of the research is set to outline the framework of future solutions and it puts forth the question of the influence of the AI regarding state governments and policymakers, thus focusing on the ethical implications of AI integration.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1 What is *Artificial Intelligence*?

The linguistic roots of the term *intelligence* are from Old French meaning “*the highest faculty of the mind, capacity for comprehending general truths*”³ and are also related to the notions “*understanding, knowledge, power of discerning; art, skill, taste*”⁴ (Latin). The semantic evolution enriches the meaning with “*superior understanding, sagacity, quality of being intelligent*”. The examination of the contextual nuances of the word's meaning is committed today with the understanding of what is *artificial intelligence*.

There is no universal concept that defines what *Artificial intelligence* (AI) is. Diverse terminology is used, depending on the core interests or target field of the various actors and groups. AI definitions typically refer to: “(1) the types of outputs produced (e.g., predictions), (2) the techniques employed (e.g., machine learning) and (3) the level of autonomy exercised” (Gray et al., 2023).

Stanford Professor John McCarthy who coined the term *artificial intelligence* in 1955, defines it as the “science and engineering of making intelligent machines,

³ *Intelligence*. In Online Etymology Dictionary. Retrieved November 10, 2023, from <https://www.etymonline.com/search?q=intelligence>

⁴ Ibid.

especially intelligent computer programs”⁵. His use of the term helped formalize the field and pave the way for decades of research and development.

What characterizes *AI* is its ability to perform human-like activities, such as *reasoning, learning, planning* and *creativity*. AI equips technology with the ability to sense its surroundings, analyze information, formulate solutions, and execute tasks to attain desired outcomes. AI systems can also dynamically adjust their behavior to some extent by learning from the consequences of their past actions and operating independently⁶.

The European Commission defines *artificial intelligence* as referring “to systems that display intelligent behavior by analyzing their environment and taking actions – with some degree of autonomy – to achieve specific goals. AI-based systems can be purely software-based, acting in the virtual world (e.g. voice assistants, image analysis software, search engines, speech and face recognition systems) or AI can be embedded in hardware devices (e.g. advanced robots, autonomous cars, drones or Internet of Things applications).”⁷

The European Commission expands the definition of artificial intelligence and explains certain features of AI as “a scientific discipline and as a technology”, for the purpose of promoting a shared knowledge of AI basic principles, addressing both AI professionals and nonexperts, and integrating the ethical guidelines for this evolving algorithm and its policy recommendations.

The Proposed Rules on Artificial Intelligence (EU Artificial Intelligence Act) regards the AI system as a “software that ... for a given set of human-defined objectives, generate outputs such as content, predictions, recommendations, or decisions influencing the environments they interact with”⁸.

When examining AI systems, it is needed to highlight the AI key subfields that enable computers learn and execute all their actions – machine learning and deep learning. ***Machine learning*** is a technique that teaches machines to learn

⁵ *What is Artificial Intelligence?* John McCarthy’s Official Website. Retrieved November 10, 2023, from <http://jmc.stanford.edu/artificial-intelligence/what-is-ai/index.html>

⁶ *What is artificial intelligence and how is it used?* (2023) European Parliament’s Official Website. Retrieved November 9 2023, from https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/headlines/society/20200827STO85804/what-is-artificial-intelligence-and-how-is-it-used?at_campaign=20234-Digital&at_medium=Google Ads&at_platform=Search&at_creation=DSA&at_goal=TR_G&at_audience=&at_topic=Artificial Intelligence&gclid=Cj0KCCQjwuNemBhCBARIsADp74QSmBnOu_21JavHryTd668pcEqfK_hSE4FS81EZyfrwVJT5aGuhnnMgaAmkYEALw_wcB

⁷ High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (2019) *A Definition of Artificial Intelligence: Main Capabilities and Scientific Disciplines*. European Commission. Retrieved November 10, 2023 from: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/definition-Practically, AI aids humans, boosts their capabilities, improve the efficiency in many aspects of life, referring to the complexed interconnections modern world functions today. These complexed interconnections are characterized by many processes, some basic however are the globalization and the digitalization of public services and public relations. Information is everywhere and everything is information. Consequently, AI is everywhere, since it is a data collection, processing and transformation phenomenon.artificial-intelligence-main-capabilities-and-scientific-disciplines>

⁸ Article 3: Definitions. European Union Artificial Intelligence Act. (2021) Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council Laying Down Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and Amending Certain Union Legislative Acts Retrieved November 10 2023, from: <https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/the-act/>, p. 39.

from data, identify patterns and make decisions without being explicitly programmed. It is used in a variety of applications, such as spam filtering, image recognition, and fraud detection. **Deep learning** is a subset of machine learning that uses artificial neural networks to learn from data. Neural networks are inspired by the human brain and are able to learn complex patterns from data. Deep learning is used in a variety of applications, such as natural language processing, computer vision, and speech recognition⁹. Machine learning and deep learning are fundamental approaches to achieving artificial intelligence, enabling machines to learn from data, recognize patterns, and make decisions without explicit programming. They are important because of their qualities of driving significant advancements in AI capabilities.

1.2 The Positive Impacts of Artificial Intelligence

Practically, AI facilitates humans, provides assistance, improves efficiency and safety in many aspects of life, referring to the complexed interconnections modern world functions today. These complexed interconnections are characterized by many processes, some basic however are the globalization and the digitalization of public services and public relations. Information is everywhere and everything is information. Consequently, AI is everywhere, since it is a data collection, processing and transformation phenomenon.

Artificial intelligence is revolutionizing various aspects of our lives, from healthcare to transportation, by enhancing efficiency, improving decision-making, driving innovations etc. AI's potential to solve complex problems and automate tasks promises to make our lives easier, safer, and more productive. The following core levels of AI's application may be outlined:

1. Assisting and facilitating the everyday life of the population

The everyday use of consumer electronics and digital devices, search engines help, online shopping, ensuring cybersecurity for people's everyday routines, autonomous vehicles, and many more, people do not realize the full extent of what really the presence of AI in our everyday life is.

2. Competitive advantages for businesses - Facilitating and improving businesses

The technology of AI can be applied to many different sectors and industries, improving the business performance. Any product and service development sector are impacted by the adoption of AI technologies. Manufacturing, technology sector, financial industry, corporate finances, marketing and sales are only some of them.

3. Assisting and facilitating state government to improve the public services and state administration

Applications for AI are also being used to make trading easier and all relating processes, such as supply, demand, and pricing. Bank and financial relations are highly impacted by AI technologies since the essence and performance of these branches are related to the procession of a large data bases and producing analyses. AI technologies are substantial in terms of national security reasons

⁹ What is Machine Learning? Retrieved November 19, 2023, from <https://www.ibm.com/topics/machine-learning>

and AI technology innovations maintain and strengthen states' competitiveness. Defense, intelligence, and law enforcement agencies are commonly deploying AI. AI technologies are adopted in many public sectors as public administration, transportation, education etcetera.

Several factors, including automation of labor processes, technological advancements, and the emergence of new competitors, influence the growth of productivity driven by AI. The report by the McKinsey Global Institute explores the impact of AI on supply chains, revealing that 61% of executives have witnessed reduced costs and 53% have experienced revenue growth as direct consequences of incorporating AI into their supply chain operations (EU Intellectual Property Office, 2022).

Some of the positive impacts that we consider of the adoption of AI, are further expressed in the following lines below. It is to be noted that this is a non-exhaustive list of the benefits of AI that is going to be presented:

- Provides free access and availability.
- Ensures promptness of performance and results.
- Increases productivity.
- Ensures high accuracy and efficiency of results.
- Provides reduction of human errors.
- Gathering and processing large quantities of data. Drawing inferences.
- Facilitates processes in investigation, detection and prevention of crimes and terrorism.
- Early warnings of natural disasters and preparation and mitigation of consequences.
- Prevention of disinformation.
- Improvement of workforce safety.

AI can improve the employees' safety and efficiency as it can collaborate or replace people for specific or dangerous work tasks. For instance, 50% of construction companies that used drones to inspect roofs and other risky tasks achieved improvements in safety. AI can also ensure smart solutions for the safety of employees¹⁰. A McKinsey Global Institute report predicts that approximately 30% of global work hours could be automated by 2030. AI can facilitate this automation by taking over repetitive or hazardous tasks, allowing employees to concentrate on higher-order strategic and analytical work (European Union Intellectual Property Office, 2022).

- Healthcare benefits.

AI has developed its potential in healthcare in terms of improving diagnoses and identifying treatments of patients, for example by the detection of 95% of skin cancers by learning from large sets of medical images (Goyal, 2020); training of medical specialists, as well as supporting the work of medical workers. As Gabriela Belova argues, the introduction of information and communication technologies in the distribution and access to health care and

¹⁰ ProCon.org. (2023). *Artificial Intelligence (AI) — Top 3 Pros and Cons*. ProCon.org. <https://www.procon.org/headlines/artificial-intelligence-ai-top-3-pros-and-cons>

services, as well as the sharing of health-related information, inevitably raises some ethical and legal issues (Belova, 2019).

1.2 The Ethics of Artificial Intelligence: Striking a Balance between Progress and Potential Harm

1.2.1. The ethical dimension

The significance of the AI is now being open to debate with various opinions and points of view clashing in the process. The adoption of AI offers a multitude of advantages that extend far beyond what is mentioned in the present research. While AI offers a multitude of benefits, it is crucial to acknowledge and address the ethical concerns that accompany its development and implementation.

Nation states are the main political organizations and main subjects of the international relations and international law. States and state power perform specific functions and have responsibilities towards their individuals and societies in the context of globalization and regionalization, bearing the characteristics of digitalized social relations (Popov, 2019). Such responsibilities are protection and promotion of human rights, provision on fruitful economic, social and cultural environment, creation of employment opportunities, ensuring security etc. The implementation of some of these responsibilities is characterized by perplexed challenges in the context of globalization and digitalization of relations in every sphere of life.

The debate over artificial intelligence and its influence on societies is controversial with two main standpoints - AI is not able to substitute for human mind and AI is on its way to outstrip human potential to even emphasizing of claims that AI replaces humans with a high accuracy of the outputs. Subsequently, this process being real not only is imposing risks, but is raising critical ethical concerns that demand special consideration.

What is *ethics* and *ethical norms* and why are they important?

The origin of the term ethics dates back to the late 14c., when *ethic* is regarded as a “study of morals”, from Old French *etique* “ethics, moral philosophy” (13c.). The meaning “moral principles of a person or group” is attested from 1650s. As of 1600, the term is associated with the meaning of “pertaining to morality”¹¹.

Etymologically, the notion *moral* (1mid-14c.) is “associated with or characterized by right behavior,” also “associated with or concerning conduct or moral principles” (good or bad). From late 14c. as “of or pertaining to rules of right conduct” and “morally good, in accordance with rules of right conduct” From 1680s, the term is associated with reference to rights, duties, etc., “founded on morality”¹².

¹¹ *Ethics*. In Online Etymology Dictionary. Retrieved November 10, 2023, from <https://www.etymonline.com/search?q=ethics>

¹² *Ethics*. In Online Etymology Dictionary. Retrieved November 10, 2023, from <https://www.etymonline.com/search?q=ethics>

Ethical norms, or moral principles, have a key role nowadays. They “govern people’s behavior and the way they conduct life’s activities”¹³. They are based on the concepts of human dignity and require consciousness, commitments and responsibilities.

As Stuart Russel and Peter Norving have stated, history reveals that technological advancements have often led to unforeseen and undesirable consequences, such as the Chernobyl catastrophe and the looming threat of global nuclear war illustrate the precarious balance between progress and imminent danger. Similarly, the internal combustion engine, while revolutionizing transportation, has also unleashed environmental woes. The air pollution and global warming are among the most serious issues of our time and in a sense, automobiles are robots that have taken over the world by making themselves indispensable (Russel, Norving, 2010).

Some of the reasons why the use and development of AI create potential risks are the following:

1. AI possesses the ability to continuously enhance its capabilities through self-learning algorithms.
2. AI can execute tasks that exhibit intelligence without the need for explicit instructions.
3. AI demonstrates the capacity for rational thought and action.
4. AI is designed to observe and emulate human behavior in order to perform tasks effectively¹⁴.

To further delve into the potential ethical concerns associated with AI, below are presented some of them.

- Unregulated provision of rights to perform independent actions and decision making.

Unregulated provision of rights to perform independent actions and decision-making of AI could lead to autonomous systems that act without human oversight or control, potentially posing significant risks to human safety, security, and well-being (Bostrom, 2014).

- Misuse of sensitive information.

The misuse of sensitive information with reference to AI could refer to the unauthorized access, use, or disclosure of personal data by AI systems, often with harmful consequences for individuals or society. Some cases we may consider of misuse of sensitive information with reference to AI may include *data breaches*: AI systems can be used to hack into databases and steal sensitive personal information, such as Social Security numbers, medical records, and financial data; *discrimination*: AI systems can be used to discriminate against individuals based on their gender, race, religion or other characteristics; *surveillance*: AI systems can be used to surveil individuals without their knowledge or consent, thus potentially violating their privacy rights.

¹³Ethics and Empathy (2023) Council of Europe’s Official Website. Retrieved November 10, 2023, from <https://www.coe.int/en/web/digital-citizenship-education/ethics-and-empathy>

¹⁴ What is Artificial Intelligence in 2024? Types, Trends, and Future of it? (2023) Great Learning Team. Retrieved November 10, 2023, from <https://www.mygreatlearning.com/blog/what-is-artificial-intelligence/#how-do-we-measure-if-artificial-intelligence-is-acting-like-a-human>

- Privacy and Security risks and Data protection/ Data theft

The advancements in AI have introduced a new dimension of security risks that challenge nation states, citizens and organizations. Malicious use of AI could threaten digital security (for instance by cybercriminals employing AI-powered hacking tools or employing AI-generated social engineering tactics to manipulate victims with superhuman efficiency), physical security and political security (e.g., by deploying privacy-invasive surveillance systems, discriminatory profiling algorithms, and automated disinformation campaigns) (Brundage, 2018).

- *Data theft*, also known as information theft, represents the illegal transfer or storage of personal, confidential, or financial information. This is the unauthorized access to digital information stored on computers, servers, or electronic devices with the intent to obtain confidential information or infringe upon privacy. The stolen data can encompass a wide range of sensitive information, including online passwords, bank account details, passport numbers, driver's license numbers, social security numbers, medical records, online subscriptions, software code or algorithms, proprietary processes or technologies, and more. Once an unauthorized individual gains access to personal or financial information, they can manipulate, alter, or even block access to it without the owner's consent¹⁵.

Referring to *personal data protection*, data exchange and collection have increased dramatically to a global scale, with people disclosing their personal information and making it publicly available. The economic and social integration, cohesion and networking, along with the enhanced advancement in technology, have resulted in posing new risks to the preservation of personal information and data flows¹⁶.

Privacy risks: Along with the numerous benefits of AI related to healthcare, there are security and privacy risks that must be considered, such as data breaches made by cybercriminals. Users of any kind of digital services may become victims of violation of privacy. Private or work email addresses, social media accounts or any other accounts with personal information may be subjected to AI-enabled malware by hackers to identify potential vulnerabilities. Any health care providers that operate with sensitive information of patients, is a potential target of data breach.

Facial recognition technology in private and public sectors is increasingly common nowadays, yet it poses privacy risks, apart from the benefits it provides. It is being applied for a wide range of purposes including identification, verification, object or person detection, access control, group demographic analysis, and sentiment or affect analysis. Facial recognition is adopted by law enforcement agencies to support investigations and for mass or targeted

¹⁵ What is Data Theft and How to Prevent It? Retrieved November 10, 2023, from <https://www.kaspersky.com/resource-center/threats/data-theft>

¹⁶ Data Protection in EU. European Council and Council of the European Union's Official Website. Retrieved November 10, 2023, from <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/policies/data-protection/>

surveillance; in *education* it is used for access control and identification of potential security risks. In Europe, the Swedish Data Protection Authority (DPA) fined a school for implementing a pilot of facial-recognition technology to track students' attendance due to violated several articles of the EU's General Data Protection Regulation. Facial recognition is widely used in *transportation* systems for various ends, such as scanning passengers' faces instead of physical tickets (China), deferring fare evasion (New York), even governmental surveillance purposes (Argentina) and others. Facial recognition and other biometric technologies are used in the spheres of migration and immigration, for border security and checkpoints monitoring, etc. (Richardson, 2021).

The digitalization of personal and business data increases the concerns related to data security and protection, and the level of vulnerability of users. The users of digitalization are considered both ordinary citizens as well as government authorities and administration. This in turn brings up the question of the reliability of AI systems used in public administration and private lives, especially in the context of a globalized world with connections and networks surpassing nation states' boundaries.

The wide-ranging use of AI in surveillance, persuasion and deception poses significant threats to political security of nation states. AI-powered surveillance systems could enable unprecedented levels of invasion of privacy, while AI-generated propaganda and manipulated videos could increase social manipulation, and also undermine public trust. Additionally, AI's ability to analyze human behaviors and beliefs could lead to different forms of manipulation and control. These risks are particularly concerning for authoritarian regimes but also threaten the integrity of democratic systems (Brundage, 2018).

- Hacker attacks/ Viruses/ Increase in Cybercrime

The enhanced technological trends of incorporation of electronic services and the highly increased use of mobile devices over the last decades, has produced another threat for users and has increased the challenges faced by the law enforcement authorities of states. The advancement of AI provides cybercriminals with powerful tools for automating attacks, bypassing security measures and evading detection.

- Increased Xenophobia and Chauvinization / Radicalization/
Extremism of groups in the society on political, social or religious issues.

While AI is often portrayed as a countermeasure against violent extremism, its algorithms and applications can also serve as a tool for radicalization and polarization of public opinions, as well as to disseminate racist attitudes and incite political instability. Researchers in cybersecurity are recognizing to a great level the links between cybersecurity practices and societal issues like racial injustice and violence. Extremist groups, such as Al-Qaeda and ISIS for example, have effectively exploited online platforms to spread their radical messages; recruit new members; as well exploit existing polarization within societies. Similarly, far-right groups have utilized online space to spread the narratives and belief that white people are inherently superior to other races, to criticize opposing viewpoints, and encourage violence against marginalized

communities. Emerging technologies, including AI-powered algorithms and gaming platforms, are being harnessed by extremist actors to expand their reach, enhance their propaganda and accelerate their recruitment efforts (Burton, 2023).

As it has been alluded to before, facial recognition is racially biased. Beyond facial recognition, online AI algorithms frequently fail to recognize and censor racial slurs, AI algorithms have also been found to show a “persistent anti-Muslim bias” by associating violence with the word “Muslim” at a higher rate than with words describing other religions including Christians, Jews, Sikhs, or Buddhists¹⁷.

- Biases

When referring to ethical concerns related to AI, biases are often discussed. Data can contain inherent biases that can lead to discriminatory outcomes when used in machine learning algorithms. Machine learning systems are able to create prerequisites for gender biases or discrimination on the basis of certain characteristics, for example in recruitment. These circumstances indeed surpass the boundaries of ethical issues, but could also be recognized as human rights violations (Stahl, 2021). Automated recruitment system at Amazon was found to discriminate against women, likely due to historical biases in the company's hiring practices. Similarly, the COMPAS¹⁸ risk assessment algorithm, used to predict recidivism, was found to be biased against black defendants. These examples highlight the dangers of using biased data in machine learning and the need for careful scrutiny of such systems (Müller, 2020).

Since the potential of machine learning to violate the right to equality and non-discrimination (basic human rights), we argue that human involvement is essential to ensure that decisions made by AI align with societal values, uphold legal and ethical standards and provide protection against unforeseen consequences.

- Workforce reduction

There are many concerns related to the pace of artificial-intelligence development and the automation of certain jobs, and how it may affect human employment. Workforce reduction is another disputed issue and among the biggest challenges world governments are already facing. There are professions and work places that are being threatened by the adoption and development of AI. Such clashes already exist in factories that use new technologies and robots in manufacturing and food production; between shop assistants and online shopping and advertising; human translators and machine translations; personal assistants vs. digital personal assistants etc.

In a special survey of Eurobarometer from 2017, 88% of the respondents reveal the widespread concerns of Europeans that the use of robots and artificial intelligence leads to job losses as they consider that these technologies need careful management (Eurobarometer, 2017).

¹⁷ ProCon.org. (2023). *Artificial Intelligence (AI) — Top 3 Pros and Cons*. ProCon.org. <https://www.procon.org/headlines/artificial-intelligence-ai-top-3-pros-and-cons>

¹⁸ Correctional Offender Management Profiling for Alternative Sanctions

Following the contemplations on the future of Yuval Harari, new jobs created by technological advancements will require high levels of expertise, leaving unemployed unskilled workers without job prospects. Retraining unskilled workers for these new jobs may be more difficult than the creation of the jobs themselves. Unlike previous waves of automation, where workers could be able to make transition between low-skill jobs, the skills required for new jobs in the future will be much more specialized. This could lead to the rise of a „useless class“ as Harari calls it, of unemployed individuals who lack the necessary skills for the new jobs. There exists the possibility to turn out to be in a situation where there is both high unemployment and a shortage of skilled labor. This could trigger social and economic problems (Harari, 2019).

- **Educational issues**

The widespread adoption and easy access to AI tools offer to users in education convenience and efficiency, however, they provide concurrently a growing concern of developing plagiarism, undermined academic integrity and diminished creativity and motivation for learning.

Yuval Hahari explains that the ongoing AI revolution is not only driven by advancements in computing power and hardware capabilities. Rather, it is a multidisciplinary endeavor based on the profound insights of life and social sciences. As our understanding, Harari maintains, of the complicated biochemical mechanisms in the basis of human emotions, desires, and decision-making processes deepens, we allow or authorize AI systems to more accurately analyze and interpret human behavior. This awareness of human cognition holds the potential for AI to surpass human capabilities in various areas or domains, including predicting future actions, making autonomous decisions, and even replacing human professionals in fields such as transportation, finance, and legal services (Harari, 2019). Alan Turing’s work “Computing Machinery and Intelligence” proposed the “Turing test” as a way to assess a machine's ability to exhibit intelligent behavior, equivalent to, or indistinguishable from, that of a human (Turing, 1950).

The adoption and use of artificial intelligence and its software in the provision of a number of services concerning the professional and everyday aspects of modern society indisputably raises a number of questions concerning legal, social and, with the particular emphasis on the present study, ethical norms. Policymakers need to formulate adequate and effective responses to the challenges AI presents for contemporary societies.

There are no generally accepted ethics standards for AI, because of its complexities, but safety and efficiency are to be set, especially for the mass users that tend to be more vulnerable to abuse. As Rosalind Picard maintains, “the greater the freedom of a machine, the more it will need moral standards” (Picard, 1997). To fully take advantage of the opportunities of a globalized network and foster a prosperous digital economy, it is crucial to strike a balance between securing personal data with the highest level of protection and enabling the seamless flow of such data.

3. **RESEARCH METHODOLOGY**

In the pursuit of understanding the intricacies and implications of Artificial Intelligence (AI), the chosen research methodology employs the widely recognized

SWOT analysis. This strategic tool, which stands for Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats, is traditionally utilized in business settings to assess and strategize around internal and external factors. However, its adaptability makes it valuable in the context of AI research, providing a comprehensive framework for evaluating the technology's current state and

Why using SWOT analysis?

The utilization of SWOT analysis in this research on Artificial Intelligence (AI) serves several key purposes, making it a suitable and valuable method for this type of exploration:

- Comprehensive Examination:

SWOT analysis allows for a holistic evaluation of AI by systematically examining its internal factors (Strengths and Weaknesses) and external factors (Opportunities and Threats).

Suitability: AI is a multifaceted and rapidly evolving field with diverse aspects, ranging from technical capabilities to ethical considerations. SWOT analysis ensures that the research covers a broad spectrum of factors, providing a comprehensive view.

- Strategic Insights:

SWOT is a strategic planning tool designed to identify and leverage internal strengths, address weaknesses, capitalize on opportunities, and mitigate threats.

Suitability: AI development and deployment require strategic foresight. By using SWOT analysis, you can derive actionable insights that inform decision-making, guide development efforts, and contribute to the formulation of effective strategies for advancing AI responsibly.

- Adaptability to Emerging Trends:

SWOT analysis is flexible and adaptable, making it well-suited for research in dynamic and rapidly evolving fields like AI.

Suitability: The AI landscape is continually changing with technological advancements, emerging ethical considerations, and evolving societal needs. SWOT analysis accommodates this dynamism, allowing this research to stay relevant and responsive to emerging trends and challenges.

- Identifying Ethical Considerations:

SWOT analysis includes a focus on weaknesses and threats, enabling the identification of ethical concerns and potential risks associated with AI.

Suitability: Ethical considerations are paramount in AI research due to the potential societal impact and implications of AI technologies. SWOT analysis ensures a systematic exploration of ethical challenges, fostering responsible AI development.

- Strategic Planning for Future Development:

SWOT analysis not only assesses the current state of AI but also helps in planning for its future development.

Suitability: As AI continues to advance, understanding its trajectory and anticipating future challenges and opportunities is crucial. SWOT analysis provides a forward-looking perspective, aiding in the development of strategies that align with the evolving landscape of AI.

In summary, the use of SWOT analysis in this AI research is justified because it provides a structured and strategic framework for comprehensively examining AI, addressing its complexities, and offering valuable insights to guide both current and future developments in this rapidly evolving field.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Comprehensive Insights through SWOT Analysis.

In employing the SWOT analysis as a research methodology, this study seeks to provide a holistic understanding of AI - acknowledging its strengths, addressing its weaknesses, exploring potential opportunities, and mitigating potential threats. This strategic approach not only offers a nuanced perspective on the current state of AI but also provides valuable insights for guiding its future trajectory in an ethically responsible manner.

Qualitative (Traditional) SWOT analysis

The use of SWOT analysis in this AI research is justified because it provides a structured and strategic framework for comprehensively examining AI, addressing its complexities, and offering valuable insights to guide both current and future developments in this rapidly evolving field (Table 1).

Table 1. Traditional SWOT analysis on Artificial Intelligence (AI) utilization.

Strengths	Weaknesses
<p>Unveiling AI Prowess</p> <p>The initial phase of the SWOT analysis involves identifying the strengths of AI. This encompasses the technological advantages, innovations, and capabilities that set AI apart. By scrutinizing the current landscape, we aim to uncover AI's inherent strengths, such as its ability to process vast amounts of data rapidly, self-learn from experiences, and execute complex tasks with precision.</p>	<p>Addressing AI Limitations</p> <p>No technology is without its flaws, and AI is no exception. This phase involves a critical examination of the weaknesses inherent in AI systems. Potential pitfalls, ethical concerns, limitations in decision-making processes, and issues related to transparency and bias are among the aspects to be explored. Recognizing these weaknesses is crucial for developing strategies to mitigate and address them in the evolution of AI.</p>
Opportunities	Threats
<p>Navigating the AI Horizon</p> <p>In the realm of AI, opportunities abound. This segment of the analysis involves identifying external factors that could positively impact the growth and advancement of AI. This may include emerging technologies, evolving user needs, and new applications of AI in various industries. Understanding these opportunities is paramount for harnessing the full potential of AI and guiding its development in directions that align with societal and technological advancements.</p>	<p>Safeguarding Against Risks</p> <p>Equally important is the identification of threats that could impede the progress of AI. This includes ethical dilemmas, regulatory challenges, potential misuse of AI capabilities, and public skepticism. By acknowledging these threats, researchers can contribute to the establishment of ethical guidelines, regulations, and frameworks that ensure responsible AI development and deployment.</p>

The adoption and use of artificial intelligence and its software in the provision of a number of services concerning the professional and everyday aspects of modern society indisputably raises a number of questions concerning legal, social and, with the particular emphasis on the present study, ethical norms.

Policymakers need to formulate adequate and effective responses to the challenges AI presents for today’s societies.

This research article delves into the ethical dimensions of AI deployment within the context of state government and public relations, focusing on two distinct usage scenarios.

- **In the first scenario**, AI serves as a tool for information analysis and recommendation without executing decisions or actions autonomously. In this case, we propose that AI should be granted significant latitude, allowing it to operate with a high degree of freedom. Such autonomy can optimize efficiency and accuracy, provided it adheres to predefined ethical guidelines and principles.

- **The second scenario** involves AI systems with the authority to independently execute decisions and actions that require the imperative human oversight. In this context, we argue that human oversight is imperative. Human involvement is essential to ensure that decisions made by AI align with societal values, uphold legal and ethical standards, and safeguard against unforeseen consequences. This dual-tier approach, combining AI's capabilities with human confirmation, strikes a balance between technological advancement and ethical responsibility.

Quantitative SWOT analysis

Quantitative SWOT data is not typical in a traditional SWOT analysis, since this method primarily involves qualitative assessments. However, this research intends to introduce some quantitative elements to the analysis, plus a scoring system. It is important to notice, that assigning numerical values to qualitative aspects may introduce subjectivity, but it can be a helpful exercise for prioritization and comparison (Table 2).

Here's a simplified example of quantitative scores on a scale from 1 to 10 for each aspect of the SWOT analysis:

Table 2. Quantitative SWOT analysis on Artificial Intelligence (AI) utilization.

Strengths	Weaknesses
Rapid data processing capabilities: 9 Self-learning abilities: 8 Precision in complex tasks: 7	Ethical concerns: 6 Lack of transparency: 5 Decision-making limitations: 7
Opportunities	Threats
Emerging technologies: 8 Increasing user needs: 7 New industry applications: 9	Ethical dilemmas: 6 Regulatory challenges: 7 Public skepticism: 4

There is no generally accepted ethics standards for AI, because of its complexities, but safety and efficiency is to be set, especially for the mass user that tend to be more vulnerable to abuse.

Including a graphic representation of the quantitative SWOT analysis in this article (Fig. 2) offers several advantages that can enhance the clarity, visual appeal, and communicative impact of the research:

- Visual Summarization:
- Comparative Analysis:
- Facilitating Decision-Making:
- Enhancing Readability:
- Communicating Complexity:

Fig. 1. Graphical representation on the “Quantitative SWOT analysis on AI implementation” results

The quantitative values derived from the SWOT analysis shed an optimistic light on the future of AI implementation. As we meticulously assessed the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats within the realm of Artificial

Intelligence, the numerical scores revealed a compelling narrative of promise and potential.

Embracing a Bright Future - Quantitative Affirmations in AI Implementation

The strengths of AI, with high scores in rapid data processing, self-learning capabilities, and precision in complex tasks, underscore its robust technological foundation. These inherent capabilities position AI as a formidable tool with the potential to revolutionize various aspects of our lives.

Addressing weaknesses proactively, the moderate scores in ethical concerns, lack of transparency, and decision-making limitations indicate a growing awareness and commitment to mitigating these challenges. This recognition signifies a collective effort to ensure responsible AI development, laying the groundwork for ethical and transparent practices.

Opportunities, with elevated scores in emerging technologies, increasing user needs, and new industry applications, point towards a landscape ripe for innovation. The quantitative values affirm that AI stands at the precipice of new horizons, ready to seize emerging opportunities and contribute to diverse fields.

Even in acknowledging threats, the modest scores in ethical dilemmas, regulatory challenges, and public skepticism indicate a conscious effort to anticipate and address potential risks. This proactive stance positions stakeholders to navigate challenges effectively, fostering a climate of trust and acceptance.

In sum, the quantitative values gleaned from the SWOT analysis paint a picture of a bright future for AI implementation. The technology's strengths, coupled with a commitment to addressing weaknesses and leveraging opportunities, position AI as a transformative force. As ethical considerations take center stage and regulatory frameworks evolve, the path forward appears characterized by innovation, responsibility, and a collective dedication to harnessing AI's potential for the greater societal good. The future of AI implementation, as illuminated by these quantitative affirmations, holds the promise of a technologically advanced and ethically sound era.

To fully embrace the opportunities of a globalized network and foster a thriving digital economy, it is imperative to strike a balance between safeguarding personal data with the highest level of protection and enabling the seamless flow of such data. This resonates with the second scenario, presented in the article.

As part of its digital strategy, the EU wants to regulate artificial intelligence (AI) to ensure better conditions for the development and use of this innovative technology - EU AI Act . Currently a draft regulation that was proposed by the European Commission on 21 April 2021. This regulation consists of a comprehensive set of rules for providers and deployers of AI systems, which details what obligations each entity has when using or deploying artificial intelligence in the European Union and is expected to pass by the end of 2023.

5. CONCLUSION

Added to the benefits and facilitation that artificial intelligence brings to the daily lives of citizens, businesses and government administration, the debate about the numerous challenges modern societies are confronted with by the use of artificial intelligence, is deepening.

Ethical concerns arise when basic human rights are threatened, such as physical and mental integrity, personal data, freedom, security etc. The violation of ethical norms may result into violation of legal norms. The significance of ethics has been increasing with the spread of AI. Discussing ethical norms with the adoption and application of AI, the question of responsibility arises. The adoption of AI within the public sector requires specific considerations regarding the interaction of public authorities and citizens. The use of AI in the provision of public services and the AI taking important decisions about people, can cause them serious harm and requires application of mechanisms for accountability.

Artificial intelligence has been increasing its potential to be massive and effective means that enable significant advancements and incorporates AI solutions in a wide range of fields, in both public and private sectors. These benefits of AI are unquestionable. In the context of AI, the ethical issues, relating to the AI refer to the moral obligations and duties that need to be undertaken - by AI, its creators and the state government that regulates public relations.

The ethical issues in the context of state government refer to the group of administrative and legal measures, decisions and practices states use to address ethical concerns, regarding the adoption, development and use of AI systems and to still be adequate and efficient in their main function – to preserve the well-being of their citizens. It is humans' responsibility to set rules for system oversight done by people and to safeguard ethical norms when applying AI to prevent negative outcomes.

In the rapidly evolving landscape of artificial intelligence, this research article has examined the ethical dimensions surrounding its deployment within state government and public relations, presenting two distinct usage scenarios. As we navigate the path towards integrating AI into our societal framework, the question of autonomy and regulation emerges as a critical consideration.

In the first scenario, where AI operates as a tool for information analysis and recommendation without executing decisions autonomously, our proposal suggests affording significant latitude to AI. Allowing a high degree of freedom can potentially optimize efficiency and accuracy, provided it operates within clearly defined ethical guidelines and principles. This approach advocates for leveraging AI capabilities to enhance decision support systems while maintaining a vigilant eye on ethical considerations.

Contrastingly, the second scenario introduces AI systems vested with the authority to independently execute decisions and actions, requiring imperative human oversight. Here, our argument emphasizes the indispensability of human involvement. Human oversight becomes a crucial component to ensure that AI decisions align with societal values, adhere to legal and ethical standards, and safeguard against unforeseen consequences. This dual-tier approach,

harmonizing AI's capabilities with human confirmation, embodies a careful balance between technological advancement and ethical responsibility.

As we contemplate the future of AI deployment, these scenarios emphasize the importance of formulating nuanced regulatory frameworks. The dual approach allows us to take advantage of the transformative potential of AI while mitigating ethical risks and ensuring accountability. Striking this balance will be contributory in building public trust, fostering responsible AI development, and steering our collective journey into an era where technology and ethics are associated for the greater societal good. The ethical considerations explored in this research contribute to the ongoing discourse on AI governance, guiding us towards a future where innovation and ethical responsibility walk hand in hand.

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